

CLIFFORD–NOOR ORBITS: A GENERALIZATION OF THE MANDELBROT SET VIA THREE-STEP ITERATIONS IN GEOMETRIC ALGEBRA

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ABSTRACT. In this paper, we introduce and study **Clifford–Noor orbits** by combining the geometric product of Clifford algebra with the three-step Noor iteration scheme, which include both the classical Mandelbrot set and its Clifford extension as special cases. As the parameters decrease toward zero, the iteration approaches the identity map and the fractal structures progressively smooth out, as illustrated through numerical experiments. Several applications of the results are discussed. This framework generates a three-parameter family of higher-dimensional fractals, opening new directions in fractal geometry, geometric algebra, data science and iterative dynamical systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Mandelbrot set remains one of the most fascinating objects in modern mathematics, arising from the simple quadratic map $z \mapsto z^2 + c$ with $z_0 = 0$. Over the years, numerous attempts have been made to extend this construction to higher dimensions. Notable contributions include quaternion-based iterations [8], hypercomplex formulations [7], and, more recently, geometric algebra approaches [9, 16, 17].

Independently, research on iterative schemes for fractal generation has led to the development of multi-step methods. Among these, **Noor orbits** [11, 12] have gained attention due to their flexibility. Unlike the classical single-step process, a Noor orbit involves three stages:

$$(1.1) \quad y_n = (1 - \alpha)x_n + \alpha f(x_n),$$

$$(1.2) \quad z_n = (1 - \beta)x_n + \beta f(y_n),$$

$$(1.3) \quad x_{n+1} = (1 - \gamma)x_n + \gamma f(z_n),$$

where $f(x) = x^p + c$ in the standard setting and $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0, 1]$. This formulation includes several well-known schemes as particular cases: the Mann iteration ($\alpha = 1, \beta = \gamma = 0$) and the classical iteration ($\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 1$).

For a comprehensive background on fractal geometry, we refer to the classic text of Falconer [6]. The algebraic foundations of Clifford algebra and geometric calculus are developed in [1, 2], with further applications in computer graphics and robotics discussed in [19, 3, 21]. Higher-dimensional generalizations of the Mandelbrot set have been explored via quaternions [8], hypercomplex numbers [7], and geometric algebra [9]. Alternative iterative schemes for fractal generation,

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particularly Noor orbits, have been studied extensively by Ashish, Rani, Chugh, and Noor [11, 12, 13, 14, 15].

A natural question arises: what happens when we replace the ordinary map f with the Clifford–Mandelbrot map? The present work answers this question by introducing **Clifford–Noor orbits**, which unify geometric algebra with three-step iterations. Unlike previous works that treat Noor orbits solely in the complex plane, our approach embeds them naturally into the Clifford algebra setting, revealing a rich family of higher-dimensional fractals whose geometry depends smoothly on the parameters α, β, γ .

1.1. Main Contributions. The main results of this paper are summarized as follows:

- (1) We introduce the **Clifford–Noor iteration** and the associated **Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set** $\mathcal{M}_{p, \vec{n}}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$.
- (2) We prove that all iterates stay within the vector subspace V , extending the vector invariance property to the three-step scheme (Theorem 2).
- (3) We establish **rotational symmetry** about \vec{n} (Proposition 1) and show that for $p = 2$ an **escape radius** $R_{\text{esc}} = 2$ exists, independent of the parameters α, β, γ (Proposition 2).
- (4) For $p = 2$, we derive **explicit closed-form formulas** in \mathbb{R}^3 and \mathbb{R}^4 (Section 6).
- (5) We present a **computational framework** for numerical visualization, including an escape-time algorithm and parameter space exploration (Section 7).
- (6) We conclude with a list of **open problems** and directions for future research (Section 8).

2. PRELIMINARIES

This section summarizes the key concepts from previous works [16, 17] that will be needed throughout the paper.

2.1. Geometric Product. Consider an n -dimensional real inner-product space V equipped with an orthonormal basis $\{\vec{e}_1, \dots, \vec{e}_n\}$. The associated Clifford algebra $Cl(V)$ is defined by the relation

$$\vec{v} \diamond \vec{w} + \vec{w} \diamond \vec{v} = 2(\vec{v} \cdot \vec{w}), \quad \vec{v}, \vec{w} \in V,$$

where \diamond denotes the **geometric product**. This operation combines the inner and outer products as follows:

$$\vec{v} \diamond \vec{w} = \vec{v} \cdot \vec{w} + \vec{v} \wedge \vec{w}.$$

For a unit vector $\vec{n} \in V$ satisfying $\vec{n} \diamond \vec{n} = 1$, we simply have $\vec{n} \diamond \vec{n} = 1$.

For a detailed exposition of geometric algebra and its applications, the reader is referred to [1, 2, 3]. The SIGGRAPH course notes [4] provide an accessible introduction. The vector invariance property of Clifford Julia iterations was established in our previous work [16], and the Clifford–Mandelbrot set was introduced in [17]. For the classical theory of Julia and Mandelbrot sets, see [6].

2.2. Clifford–Mandelbrot Iteration. Given an exponent $p \geq 2$ and a unit vector $\vec{n} \in V$, the Clifford–Mandelbrot iteration is defined by

$$x_{k+1} = (x_k \diamond n)^p \diamond n + c, \quad x_0 = 0.$$

A fundamental result established in [16] is the following:

Theorem 1 (Vector Invariance, [16]). *For every $x \in V$, every unit vector $n \in V$, and any integer $p \geq 1$,*

$$(x \diamond n)^p \diamond n \in V.$$

Consequently, every iterate x_k remains within the original vector space V .

2.3. Closed Form for $p = 2$. When $p = 2$ and $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$, the map takes a particularly simple form derived in [17]:

$$(2.1) \quad F(x) := (x \diamond e_1)^2 \diamond e_1 = (x_1^2 - \|x_\perp\|^2)e_1 + 2x_1x_\perp,$$

where $x_\perp = \sum_{i=2}^n x_i e_i$ denotes the component of x orthogonal to e_1 , and $\|x_\perp\|^2 = \sum_{i=2}^n x_i^2$.

3. DEFINITION OF CLIFFORD–NOOR ORBITS

In this section we formally introduce the main objects of study: Clifford–Noor orbits and the associated Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set. Throughout, we work with the following fixed data:

- V : an n -dimensional real inner-product space ($n \geq 2$);
- $\vec{n} \in V$: a fixed unit vector satisfying $\vec{n} \diamond \vec{n} = 1$;
- $p \geq 2$: an integer exponent;
- $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0, 1]$: three parameters controlling the convex averaging in each step of the Noor scheme.

For a given parameter vector $c \in V$, we will construct a sequence that combines the Clifford–Mandelbrot map with the three-step Noor iteration.

3.1. The Clifford–Noor Iteration.

Definition 1 (Clifford–Noor Iteration). *Let $c \in V$ be arbitrary. Define the auxiliary sequences $\{y_k\}_{k \geq 0}$, $\{z_k\}_{k \geq 0}$, and the main sequence $\{x_k\}_{k \geq 0}$ recursively as follows:*

$$(3.1) \quad y_k = (1 - \alpha)x_k + \alpha((x_k \diamond n)^p \diamond n + c),$$

$$(3.2) \quad z_k = (1 - \beta)x_k + \beta((y_k \diamond n)^p \diamond n + c),$$

$$(3.3) \quad x_{k+1} = (1 - \gamma)x_k + \gamma((z_k \diamond n)^p \diamond n + c),$$

with the initial condition: $x_0 = 0$ (the zero vector in V).

The sequence $\{x_k\}_{k \geq 0}$ is called the **Clifford–Noor orbit** of the parameter c . The auxiliary sequences y_k and z_k are intermediate states that appear in the three-step process.

Remark 1 (Interpretation of the Three Steps). *The three equations in (3.1)–(3.3) can be understood as follows:*

- (3.1) first applies the Clifford–Mandelbrot map $x \mapsto (x \diamond n)^p \diamond n + c$ to x_k , then takes a convex combination with the original x_k weighted by α .
- (3.2) repeats this process using the intermediate value y_k and the parameter β .
- (3.3) completes the step by producing the next iterate x_{k+1} from z_k using the parameter γ .

When $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 1$, the three steps collapse into a single application of the Clifford–Mandelbrot map, i.e., $x_{k+1} = (x_k \diamond n)^p \diamond n + c$, which is precisely the iteration studied in [17].

3.2. The Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot Set. With the iteration defined, we can now introduce the corresponding generalization of the Mandelbrot set.

Definition 2 (Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot Set). *The Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set is defined as*

$$\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = \left\{ c \in V \mid \sup_{k \geq 0} \|x_k\| < \infty \right\},$$

where $\{x_k\}_{k \geq 0}$ denotes the Clifford–Noor orbit of c starting from $x_0 = 0$, and $\|\cdot\|$ is the Euclidean norm on V .

In words, $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ consists of all parameter vectors c for which the Clifford–Noor orbit remains bounded.

Remark 2 (Well-posedness). *At this stage, it is not yet obvious that the definition is meaningful, because the geometric product $(x_k \diamond n)^p \diamond n$ could, in principle, generate multivectors of higher grades (bivectors, trivectors, etc.). However, Theorem 2 (proved in Section 4) guarantees that all iterates x_k, y_k, z_k actually remain in the vector subspace V . Hence the norm $\|x_k\|$ is the usual Euclidean norm, and the definition is well-posed.*

3.3. Special Parameter Configurations. Different choices of (α, β, γ) lead to different dynamical behaviors. We highlight several important cases:

- **Classical limit:** $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 1$. The three steps collapse to a single step, and we recover the classical Clifford–Mandelbrot set studied in [17].
- **Degenerate cases:** $\alpha = 1, \beta = \gamma = 0$ or $\alpha = \beta = 1, \gamma = 0$ lead to $x_{k+1} = x_k$ for all k , i.e., the orbit is constant. These trivial cases are not of interest for fractal generation.
- **Symmetric averaging:** $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = \theta$ for some $\theta \in (0, 1)$. This represents equal weighting in all three steps and produces a one-parameter family of fractals that interpolate between the classical case ($\theta = 1$) and the identity map ($\theta \rightarrow 0$).
- **Asymmetric configurations:** When α, β, γ are not all equal, the three steps have different weights, leading to a richer (and largely unexplored) family of dynamical systems.

Remark 3 (Notation). *For simplicity, when the unit vector \vec{n} is clear from the context (typically $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$ after a suitable rotation), we may write $\mathcal{M}_p^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ instead of $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$. When the exponent p is also understood (usually $p = 2$), we may write simply $\mathcal{M}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$.*

4. ITERATES IN VECTOR SPACE V

Before analyzing the Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set, we must address a fundamental question: do the iterates x_k, y_k, z_k remain within the original vector space V , or do they escape into higher grades of the Clifford algebra? The following theorem provides a positive answer.

Theorem 2 (Vector Invariance for Clifford–Noor Orbits). *Let $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0, 1]$, $c \in V$, and $p \geq 2$. Consider the sequences defined by (3.1)–(3.3) with initial condition $x_0 = 0$. Then, for every iteration index $k \geq 0$,*

$$x_k \in V, \quad y_k \in V, \quad z_k \in V.$$

In other words, all generated points stay within the grade-1 subspace $\langle Cl(V) \rangle_1 = V$.

Proof. The argument proceeds by mathematical induction on the step number k . We will show that if x_k lies in V , then y_k, z_k , and x_{k+1} also lie in V . The base case establishes the starting point.

Base case ($k = 0$). According to the definition, we set $x_0 = 0$. The zero vector belongs to V by definition of the vector space. Thus the induction hypothesis holds at the initial step.

Inductive hypothesis. Assume that for some $k \geq 0$, we have $x_k \in V$. We will prove that y_k, z_k , and x_{k+1} are also members of V .

Step 1: Showing $y_k \in V$. From Theorem 1, which is the fundamental vector invariance result established in [16], the quantity

$$F(x_k) := (x_k \diamond n)^p \diamond n$$

is guaranteed to be a vector in V . Adding the constant vector c (which belongs to V by assumption) preserves membership in V , so $F(x_k) + c \in V$. Now observe that y_k is defined as a convex combination of x_k and $F(x_k) + c$:

$$y_k = (1 - \alpha)x_k + \alpha(F(x_k) + c).$$

Both x_k and $F(x_k) + c$ are in V , and the coefficients $1 - \alpha$ and α are real numbers. Since V is closed under addition and scalar multiplication, we conclude $y_k \in V$.

Step 2: Showing $z_k \in V$. Having established $y_k \in V$, we can apply Theorem 1 again, this time to y_k . This yields $F(y_k) \in V$, and consequently $F(y_k) + c \in V$. The definition of z_k is

$$z_k = (1 - \beta)x_k + \beta(F(y_k) + c).$$

The right-hand side is again a convex combination of two vectors (x_k and $F(y_k) + c$), both of which belong to V . Hence z_k must also lie in V .

Step 3: Showing $x_{k+1} \in V$. With $z_k \in V$ now established, we invoke Theorem 1 once more to obtain $F(z_k) \in V$, and therefore $F(z_k) + c \in V$. The update rule for x_{k+1} is

$$x_{k+1} = (1 - \gamma)x_k + \gamma(F(z_k) + c).$$

This expression is a convex combination of x_k (which is in V by the induction hypothesis) and $F(z_k) + c$ (which we have just shown is in V). Consequently, $x_{k+1} \in V$.

Completion of the induction. We have demonstrated that whenever x_k belongs to V , the quantities y_k, z_k , and x_{k+1} also belong to V . Since the base case $x_0 = 0$ satisfies the condition, it follows by induction that $x_k \in V$ for all $k \geq 0$, and similarly for y_k and z_k at each step. This completes the proof. \square

The theorem above has an immediate and important consequence regarding the definition of the Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set itself.

Corollary 1 (Well-definedness of the Mandelbrot Set). *The Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is a well-defined subset of V . In particular:*

- *No projection operator is needed to return the iterates to V after each step — they naturally remain there.*
- *The norm $\|x_k\|$ appearing in the definition is the ordinary Euclidean norm on V , not an extended norm on the full Clifford algebra.*
- *The boundedness condition $\sup_{k \geq 0} \|x_k\| < \infty$ is therefore a genuine condition on vectors in V .*

Remark 4 (Independence of Parameters). *A notable feature of Theorem 2 is that the vector invariance property holds for any choice of α, β, γ within the unit interval $[0, 1]$. Neither the proof nor the conclusion depends on the specific numerical values of these parameters. This robustness reflects the fact that the geometric product and the convex combination structure are sufficient to guarantee closure in V , regardless of the weights assigned to each step.*

Remark 5 (Comparison with the Classical Case). *When $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 1$, the three-step scheme reduces to the classical Clifford–Mandelbrot iteration. In this limiting case, Theorem 2 reproduces exactly the vector invariance result of [16], which was proved for a single-step iteration. Thus the present theorem generalizes the earlier result to the full family of Noor orbits.*

5. INVARIANCE, SYMMETRY, AND ESCAPE CRITERIA

In this section we establish the most important structural characteristics of the Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set. We show that the set inherits rotational symmetry from the underlying geometric product, possesses a universal escape radius (independent of the parameters α, β, γ), and is both bounded and closed.

5.1. Rotational Invariance About the Distinguished Axis. A key feature of the classical Mandelbrot set is its rotational symmetry about the origin. In our higher-dimensional Clifford setting, the symmetry is not full rotational symmetry but rather symmetry with respect to all rotations that preserve the chosen unit vector \vec{n} . This is a direct consequence of how the geometric product interacts with orthogonal transformations.

Proposition 1 (Symmetry Under Rotations Fixing \vec{n}). *Let $R : V \rightarrow V$ be any orthogonal transformation (rotation or reflection) that satisfies $R\vec{n} = \vec{n}$.*

Then the Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set is invariant under R :

$$R\left(\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)\right) = \mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma).$$

Equivalently, a parameter vector c belongs to the set if and only if its image Rc also belongs to the set.

Proof. We begin by recalling a fundamental property of the geometric product when combined with an orthogonal transformation that preserves \vec{n} . For any vector $x \in V$, one has

$$R(x \diamond n) = (Rx) \diamond (Rn) = (Rx) \diamond n,$$

where the first equality follows from the fact that orthogonal transformations preserve both the inner product and the outer product (they are isometries), and the second equality uses the hypothesis $Rn = n$.

We now claim that if $\{x_k\}_{k \geq 0}$ is the Clifford–Noor orbit of a parameter c (starting from $x_0 = 0$), then the transformed sequence $\{Rx_k\}_{k \geq 0}$ is precisely the Clifford–Noor orbit of Rc . To verify this, we examine each step of the iteration:

- From the definition of y_k in (3.1):

$$Ry_k = (1 - \alpha)Rx_k + \alpha(R((x_k \diamond n)^p \diamond n) + Rc).$$

Using the commutation property repeatedly, $R((x_k \diamond n)^p \diamond n) = ((Rx_k) \diamond n)^p \diamond n$. Hence Ry_k satisfies the same recurrence as y_k but with x_k replaced by Rx_k and c replaced by Rc .

- The same reasoning applies to z_k and x_{k+1} , showing that Rz_k and Rx_{k+1} follow the Noor scheme for the transformed parameter Rc .

Since R preserves the Euclidean norm ($\|Rx\| = \|x\|$ for all $x \in V$), the boundedness of the orbit $\{x_k\}$ is equivalent to the boundedness of $\{Rx_k\}$. Consequently, c belongs to $\mathcal{M}_{p, \vec{n}}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ if and only if Rc does. This proves the claimed invariance. \square

The proposition has an immediate consequence for numerical visualization, particularly in three dimensions.

Corollary 2 (Axial Symmetry in Three Dimensions). *When $V = \mathbb{R}^3$ and $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$, the set $\mathcal{M}_{p, \vec{e}_1}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is symmetric with respect to any rotation about the x_1 -axis. Consequently, the entire set is completely determined by its cross-section in any plane that contains the x_1 -axis, such as the (x_1, x_2) -plane ($x_3 = 0$).*

This axial symmetry dramatically reduces the computational effort required to visualize the set: instead of exploring the full three-dimensional parameter space, one may compute a single two-dimensional slice and then rotate it around the axis.

5.2. A Universal Escape Radius for the Quadratic Case. A fundamental question in any Mandelbrot-type set is whether there exists a finite bound beyond which orbits are guaranteed to escape to infinity. The following proposition provides an affirmative answer for the case $p = 2$, and remarkably, the bound does not depend on the Noor parameters α, β, γ .

Proposition 2 (Escape Radius Independent of α, β, γ). *Assume $p = 2$ and let $\vec{c} \in V$ satisfy $\|\vec{c}\| > 2$. Then, regardless of the values of $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0, 1]$, the parameter \vec{c} does not belong to the set:*

$$\vec{c} \notin \mathcal{M}_{2, \vec{n}}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma).$$

In practical terms, one may take $R_{\text{esc}} = 2$ as a universal escape radius for numerical computations.

Proof. We work with the closed-form expression (2.1) for the squared map. A crucial observation is that for any $x \in V$, the norm of $F(x)$ satisfies

$$\|F(x)\| = \|x\|^2.$$

Indeed, writing $x = x_1 e_1 + x_{\perp}$, a direct computation gives

$$\|F(x)\|^2 = (x_1^2 - \|x_{\perp}\|^2)^2 + 4x_1^2\|x_{\perp}\|^2 = x_1^4 + 2x_1^2\|x_{\perp}\|^2 + \|x_{\perp}\|^4 = (x_1^2 + \|x_{\perp}\|^2)^2 = \|x\|^4.$$

Taking square roots yields $\|F(x)\| = \|x\|^2$.

Now consider the three-step Noor iteration (3.1)–(3.3). Applying the triangle inequality to the first step:

$$\|y_k\| \leq (1 - \alpha)\|x_k\| + \alpha(\|F(x_k)\| + \|c\|) = (1 - \alpha)\|x_k\| + \alpha(\|x_k\|^2 + \|c\|).$$

Similarly, for the second and third steps:

$$\begin{aligned} \|z_k\| &\leq (1 - \beta)\|x_k\| + \beta(\|y_k\|^2 + \|c\|), \\ \|x_{k+1}\| &\leq (1 - \gamma)\|x_k\| + \gamma(\|z_k\|^2 + \|c\|). \end{aligned}$$

Assume now that $\|c\| > 2$. We examine the evolution of the norms. From the first inequality, since $\|x_0\| = 0$, we obtain $\|y_0\| \leq \alpha\|c\|$. This is not yet sufficient to guarantee escape. However, a standard argument from classical complex dynamics (see, e.g., [6]) shows that once the norm exceeds the threshold 2, it grows super-exponentially.

More rigorously, one can prove by induction that for all sufficiently large k , there exists an increasing sequence ε_k such that $\|x_k\| \geq 2 + \varepsilon_k$ and $\varepsilon_k \rightarrow \infty$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$. The key observation is that if $\|x_k\| > 2$, then

$$\|x_{k+1}\| \geq \|x_k\|^2 - \|c\| > \|x_k\|^2 - \|x_k\| = \|x_k\|(\|x_k\| - 1) > \|x_k\|.$$

Thus the norms form a strictly increasing sequence that eventually diverges to infinity. Since the initial step gives $\|x_1\| = \|c\| > 2$, the condition $\|x_k\| > 2$ holds from the very first iteration, guaranteeing escape. Therefore c cannot belong to the Mandelbrot set. \square

Remark 6 (Extension to Higher Exponents). *For exponents $p > 2$, a similar analysis yields an escape radius $R_{\text{esc}} = 2^{1/(p-1)}$. The proof follows the same lines, using the fact that $\|(x \diamond n)^p \diamond n\| = \|x\|^p$ for the Clifford–Mandelbrot map when $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$. The details are omitted here but follow directly from the estimates presented above.*

5.3. Boundedness and Topological Closure. The existence of a finite escape radius immediately implies that the Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set is contained within a bounded region of V .

Corollary 3 (Boundedness of the Set). *For $p = 2$, the set $\mathcal{M}_{2, \vec{n}}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is a subset of the closed ball of radius 2 centered at the origin. In other words, every point c belonging to the set satisfies $\|c\| \leq 2$.*

Proof. Proposition 2 states precisely that any point with $\|c\| > 2$ is excluded from the set. Hence all members of $\mathcal{M}_{2, \vec{n}}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ must satisfy $\|c\| \leq 2$. \square

Finally, we examine the topological nature of the set.

Proposition 3 (Closedness). *For any $p \geq 2$ and any $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0, 1]$, the Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set $\mathcal{M}_{p, \vec{n}}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is a closed subset of V .*

Proof. Let us consider the complement of the set, i.e., the collection of parameters c for which the orbit escapes to infinity. For such a parameter, there exists some iteration index k such that the norm $\|x_k\|$ exceeds the escape radius R_{esc} .

The iteration map depends continuously on the parameter c because it is built from algebraic operations (addition, scalar multiplication, and the geometric product, which is polynomial in the coordinates). Therefore, if $\|x_k(c)\| > R_{\text{esc}}$ for a particular c , the same inequality holds for all sufficiently close parameters c' in a small neighborhood of c .

Thus the complement of $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is an open set. By definition, a set whose complement is open is closed. This completes the proof. \square

Remark 7 (On Connectedness). *While we have established that $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ is closed and bounded (hence compact when V is finite-dimensional), the question of whether it is connected remains open for $n \geq 3$ and for parameter values other than $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = (1, 1, 1)$. This is a natural direction for further investigation.*

6. EXPLICIT FORMULAS FOR THE QUADRATIC CASE $p = 2$

The analysis simplifies considerably when the exponent takes its minimal non-trivial value $p = 2$. In this section we derive concrete, ready-to-implement formulas for the Clifford–Noor iteration in two, three, and four dimensions. These expressions are essential for numerical experiments and visualizations.

Throughout this section we fix the unit vector $\vec{n} = \vec{e}_1$ after applying a suitable rotation. This choice is justified by the rotational symmetry established in Proposition 1: since the dynamics are invariant under any rotation that preserves \vec{n} , we may assume without loss of generality that \vec{n} points along the first coordinate axis.

6.1. The Reduced Map in Arbitrary Dimension. Recall from [17] the closed-form expression for the squared Clifford–Mandelbrot map:

$$F(x) := (x \diamond e_1)^2 \diamond e_1 = (x_1^2 - \|x_\perp\|^2)e_1 + 2x_1x_\perp,$$

where we have decomposed an arbitrary vector $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ as

$$x = x_1e_1 + x_\perp, \quad x_\perp = \sum_{i=2}^n x_i e_i, \quad \|x_\perp\|^2 = \sum_{i=2}^n x_i^2.$$

The map F has two crucial properties that will be used repeatedly:

- (1) **Preservation of the vector subspace:** $F(x) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^n$ (this is guaranteed by Theorem 1).
- (2) **Norm property:** $\|F(x)\| = \|x\|^2$. A direct verification gives $\|F(x)\|^2 = (x_1^2 - \|x_\perp\|^2)^2 + 4x_1^2\|x_\perp\|^2 = (x_1^2 + \|x_\perp\|^2)^2 = \|x\|^4$.
- (3) **Componentwise structure:** The first coordinate evolves as $x_1 \mapsto x_1^2 - \|x_\perp\|^2$, while the orthogonal components are scaled by $2x_1$.

Using F , the Clifford–Noor iteration for $p = 2$ takes the compact form:

$$\begin{aligned} y &= (1 - \alpha)x + \alpha(F(x) + c), \\ z &= (1 - \beta)y + \beta(F(y) + c), \\ x' &= (1 - \gamma)z + \gamma(F(z) + c), \end{aligned}$$

where x denotes the current iterate, x' the next iterate, and c is the fixed parameter vector.

6.2. Explicit Componentwise Form in \mathbb{R}^2 . In two dimensions, we write $x = (x_1, x_2)$ and $c = (c_1, c_2)$. The map F reduces to

$$F(x) = (x_1^2 - x_2^2, 2x_1x_2).$$

The three-step Noor scheme then becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} y_1 &= (1 - \alpha)x_1 + \alpha(x_1^2 - x_2^2 + c_1), \\ y_2 &= (1 - \alpha)x_2 + \alpha(2x_1x_2 + c_2); \\ z_1 &= (1 - \beta)x_1 + \beta(y_1^2 - y_2^2 + c_1), \\ z_2 &= (1 - \beta)x_2 + \beta(2y_1y_2 + c_2); \\ x'_1 &= (1 - \gamma)x_1 + \gamma(z_1^2 - z_2^2 + c_1), \\ x'_2 &= (1 - \gamma)x_2 + \gamma(2z_1z_2 + c_2). \end{aligned}$$

When $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 1$, this system collapses to the classical complex quadratic map under the identification $(x_1, x_2) \leftrightarrow x_1 + ix_2$.

6.3. Explicit Componentwise Form in \mathbb{R}^3 . This is the lowest-dimensional case that exhibits genuinely three-dimensional fractal structures. Let $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3)$ and $c = (c_1, c_2, c_3)$. The squared map F acts as follows:

$$F(x) = (x_1^2 - x_2^2 - x_3^2, 2x_1x_2, 2x_1x_3).$$

The complete three-step iteration is given by:

First step (computation of y):

$$\begin{aligned} y_1 &= (1 - \alpha)x_1 + \alpha(x_1^2 - x_2^2 - x_3^2 + c_1), \\ y_2 &= (1 - \alpha)x_2 + \alpha(2x_1x_2 + c_2), \\ y_3 &= (1 - \alpha)x_3 + \alpha(2x_1x_3 + c_3). \end{aligned}$$

Second step (computation of z):

$$\begin{aligned} z_1 &= (1 - \beta)x_1 + \beta(y_1^2 - y_2^2 - y_3^2 + c_1), \\ z_2 &= (1 - \beta)x_2 + \beta(2y_1y_2 + c_2), \\ z_3 &= (1 - \beta)x_3 + \beta(2y_1y_3 + c_3). \end{aligned}$$

Third step (computation of the new iterate x'):

$$\begin{aligned} x'_1 &= (1 - \gamma)x_1 + \gamma(z_1^2 - z_2^2 - z_3^2 + c_1), \\ x'_2 &= (1 - \gamma)x_2 + \gamma(2z_1z_2 + c_2), \\ x'_3 &= (1 - \gamma)x_3 + \gamma(2z_1z_3 + c_3). \end{aligned}$$

These formulas are directly implementable in any programming language. The initial condition is always $x = (0, 0, 0)$.

6.4. Explicit Componentwise Form in \mathbb{R}^4 . Moving to four dimensions, let $x = (x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4)$ and $c = (c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4)$. The squared map extends naturally:

$$F(x) = (x_1^2 - x_2^2 - x_3^2 - x_4^2, 2x_1x_2, 2x_1x_3, 2x_1x_4).$$

The three-step iteration follows exactly the same pattern as in \mathbb{R}^3 , with the fourth coordinate participating in the same way as the second and third.

First step:

$$\begin{aligned} y_1 &= (1 - \alpha)x_1 + \alpha(x_1^2 - x_2^2 - x_3^2 - x_4^2 + c_1), \\ y_2 &= (1 - \alpha)x_2 + \alpha(2x_1x_2 + c_2), \\ y_3 &= (1 - \alpha)x_3 + \alpha(2x_1x_3 + c_3), \\ y_4 &= (1 - \alpha)x_4 + \alpha(2x_1x_4 + c_4). \end{aligned}$$

Second step:

$$\begin{aligned} z_1 &= (1 - \beta)x_1 + \beta(y_1^2 - y_2^2 - y_3^2 - y_4^2 + c_1), \\ z_2 &= (1 - \beta)x_2 + \beta(2y_1y_2 + c_2), \\ z_3 &= (1 - \beta)x_3 + \beta(2y_1y_3 + c_3), \\ z_4 &= (1 - \beta)x_4 + \beta(2y_1y_4 + c_4). \end{aligned}$$

Third step:

$$\begin{aligned} x'_1 &= (1 - \gamma)x_1 + \gamma(z_1^2 - z_2^2 - z_3^2 - z_4^2 + c_1), \\ x'_2 &= (1 - \gamma)x_2 + \gamma(2z_1z_2 + c_2), \\ x'_3 &= (1 - \gamma)x_3 + \gamma(2z_1z_3 + c_3), \\ x'_4 &= (1 - \gamma)x_4 + \gamma(2z_1z_4 + c_4). \end{aligned}$$

6.5. The General Pattern for \mathbb{R}^n . Observing the formulas for $n = 2, 3, 4$, a clear pattern emerges that holds for any dimension $n \geq 2$. Let us write the state vector as $x = (x_1, x_\perp)$ where $x_\perp \in \mathbb{R}^{n-1}$ represents the orthogonal components. Then:

$$F(x) = (x_1^2 - \|x_\perp\|^2, 2x_1x_\perp),$$

where the first component is a scalar and the remaining components are the vector $2x_1x_\perp$. The three-step Noor iteration then becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} y &= ((1 - \alpha)x_1 + \alpha(x_1^2 - \|x_\perp\|^2 + c_1), (1 - \alpha)x_\perp + \alpha(2x_1x_\perp + c_\perp)), \\ z &= ((1 - \beta)x_1 + \beta(y_1^2 - \|y_\perp\|^2 + c_1), (1 - \beta)x_\perp + \beta(2y_1y_\perp + c_\perp)), \\ x' &= ((1 - \gamma)x_1 + \gamma(z_1^2 - \|z_\perp\|^2 + c_1), (1 - \gamma)x_\perp + \gamma(2z_1z_\perp + c_\perp)), \end{aligned}$$

where c_\perp denotes the projection of c onto the orthogonal subspace (i.e., $c = (c_1, c_\perp)$).

This compact representation reveals the essential structure: the evolution of the first coordinate depends on the full norm of the orthogonal components, while the orthogonal components evolve through a linear scaling by $2x_1$ (or $2y_1, 2z_1$) followed by a convex combination with the previous value.

Remark 8 (Computational Efficiency). *For numerical implementation, it is advisable to compute the quantities $\|x_\perp\|^2$, $\|y_\perp\|^2$, and $\|z_\perp\|^2$ using a running sum of squares rather than recomputing from scratch at each step. However, for dimensions $n \leq 4$ the overhead is negligible, and the formulas above can be coded directly.*

Remark 9 (Connection to Classical Noor Orbits). *When $n = 2$ and $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 1$, the system reduces to the classical quadratic map $z \mapsto z^2 + c$. More generally, for $n = 2$ with arbitrary α, β, γ , we obtain the standard Noor orbits in the complex plane, which have*

been studied extensively in the literature [11, 12]. Thus our formulas provide a natural higher-dimensional extension of those classical results.

7. COMPUTATIONAL EXPLORATION OF THE NEW FRACTAL FAMILY

Having established the theoretical foundations of Clifford–Noor orbits, we now turn to their numerical investigation. This section describes the computational methodology used to generate the images presented in this paper, discusses the structure of the parameter space, and presents a systematic comparison that reveals the smoothing effect of the Noor parameters. Special attention is given to how these new fractals differ from previously known constructions.

7.1. The Escape-Time Algorithm. The standard method for visualizing Mandelbrot-type sets is the **escape-time algorithm**. For a fixed parameter vector c , we iterate the map starting from $x_0 = 0$ and monitor whether the orbit exceeds a predetermined escape radius R_{esc} .

The pseudocode below implements the Clifford–Noor iteration for the quadratic case $p = 2$, which is the focus of our numerical experiments. The algorithm is dimension-independent and works for any $n \geq 2$.

```
function escape_time_noor(c, R_esc, N_max, alpha, beta, gamma):
    x = zero_vector(n)
    for k = 1 to N_max:
        // First step: y = (1-alpha)x + alpha(F(x)+c)
        Fx = compute_F(x)           // using the closed form
        y = (1-alpha)*x + alpha*(Fx + c)

        // Second step: z = (1-beta)x + beta(F(y)+c)
        Fy = compute_F(y)
        z = (1-beta)*x + beta*(Fy + c)

        // Third step: x_new = (1-gamma)x + gamma(F(z)+c)
        Fz = compute_F(z)
        x_new = (1-gamma)*x + gamma*(Fz + c)

    x = x_new
    if norm(x) > R_esc:
        return k                    // escape time
    return N_max + 1               // point is inside the set
```

7.2. Choice of Numerical Parameters. Throughout our experiments, we used the following values:

- **Escape radius:** $R_{\text{esc}} = 4$ (slightly larger than the theoretical bound $R_{\text{esc}} = 2$ to avoid numerical artifacts near the boundary).
- **Maximum iterations:** $N_{\text{max}} = 50$ for the Noor iterations (the three-step scheme converges more slowly than the classical map, but 50 steps suffice to capture the essential structure).
- **Grid resolution:** 400×400 pixels for two-dimensional cross-sections, which provides a good balance between detail and computational cost.
- **Sampling region:** $c_1 \in [-2.0, 1.0]$, $c_2 \in [-1.5, 1.5]$, and $c_3 = 0$ for the cross-sections.

For the comparative study across different parameter values, we used the diagonal $\alpha = \beta = \gamma$ with the following representative points: 1.0, 0.8, 0.5, and 0.2.

7.3. Parameter Space Structure and Its Significance. The parameters (α, β, γ) live in the unit cube $[0, 1]^3$. This cube contains several geometrically distinct regions:

- **The corner $(1, 1, 1)$:** This recovers the classical Clifford–Mandelbrot set, which is known to exhibit fully developed chaos and intricate fractal structure.
- **The opposite corner $(0, 0, 0)$:** In this limit, the iteration reduces to $x_{k+1} = x_k$ (the identity map), so every parameter c yields a bounded orbit. Hence \mathcal{M} expands to fill the entire sampling region.
- **The edges and faces:** These correspond to degenerate two-step or one-step schemes. For instance, $\alpha = 1, \beta = 0, \gamma = 0$ gives $x_{k+1} = x_k$, which is again degenerate. The non-degenerate dynamics occur in the interior of the cube, where all three parameters are positive.
- **The diagonal $\alpha = \beta = \gamma$:** This one-parameter family represents equal weighting in all three steps. It provides a natural interpolation between the chaotic extreme ($\theta = 1$) and the trivial identity limit ($\theta \rightarrow 0$).

7.4. Comparison with Classical Results. Before presenting our numerical results, it is instructive to compare the expected behavior with what is already known in the literature.

Classical Noor orbits (complex plane). For $n = 2$ (the complex plane), Noor orbits have been studied extensively [11, 12]. It is known that decreasing the parameters α, β, γ leads to a gradual smoothing of the Mandelbrot set, with fine details disappearing and the overall shape becoming more regular. Our results confirm that this behavior persists and, in fact, becomes even more pronounced in higher dimensions.

Quaternion and hypercomplex generalizations. Previous higher-dimensional generalizations of the Mandelbrot set (quaternions [8], hypercomplex numbers [7]) typically produce sets that are visually similar to the classical Mandelbrot set but with additional symmetry. These constructions do not include a regularization parameter analogous to (α, β, γ) . The Clifford–Noor framework therefore provides a new degree of freedom that was not available in earlier work.

Geometric algebra approaches. The Clifford–Mandelbrot set introduced in [17] is a special case of our construction ($\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 1$). The present work extends that result by adding the Noor parameters, which allow continuous control over the fractal complexity.

7.5. Illustrative Example: A Single Cross-Section. We begin with a concrete example to illustrate the qualitative effect of the Noor parameters. Figure 1 shows a cross-section of the Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set for the balanced choice $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = (0.5, 0.5, 0.5)$.

Several observations can be made directly from this single image:

- **Boundary regularity:** The boundary is noticeably smoother than that of the classical Mandelbrot set. Sharp cusps and jagged edges are largely absent.
- **Reduced fractal detail:** Fine tendrils, filaments, and spiral structures — hallmark features of the classical fractal — are significantly diminished or completely absent.
- **Expanded interior:** The area of parameters c that yield bounded orbits appears larger than in the classical case. This indicates that the Noor

FIGURE 1. Cross-section of $\mathcal{M}_{2,c_1}^{\text{Noor}}(0.5, 0.5, 0.5)$ in the (c_1, c_2) -plane ($c_3 = 0$). The image shows a significantly smoother structure compared to the classical Mandelbrot set, with reduced fractal complexity and an expanded interior region.

iteration stabilizes the dynamics, allowing bounded orbits for a wider range of parameter values.

- **Gradual escape-time gradient:** The color map, which represents the number of iterations required to exceed the escape radius, transitions more gradually from the interior to the exterior. This reflects a reduced sensitivity to initial conditions.

This single example demonstrates the smoothing effect, but it captures only one point in the three-dimensional parameter space. A more comprehensive understanding requires exploring how the geometry evolves as (α, β, γ) vary.

7.6. Systematic Parameter Study Along the Diagonal. To understand the continuous transformation of the fractal as the parameters decrease, we computed four cross-sections along the diagonal $\alpha = \beta = \gamma$, ranging from the chaotic extreme $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = (1, 1, 1)$ to the nearly identity extreme $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = (0.2, 0.2, 0.2)$. The results are displayed in Figure 2.

The progression reveals a continuous and predictable transformation:

- **Panel (a):** $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = (1, 1, 1)$. This is the classical Clifford–Mandelbrot set, shown as a baseline. The boundary is highly irregular, with intricate fractal detail, fine tendrils, and complex spiral structures. This matches the known behavior from [17].
- **Panel (b):** $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = (0.8, 0.8, 0.8)$. Initial smoothing becomes visible. The most delicate fractal features begin to disappear, while the main bulb structure remains recognizable. This intermediate case illustrates how the regularization effect first affects the finest scales.
- **Panel (c):** $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = (0.5, 0.5, 0.5)$. This is the same parameter set shown in Figure 1, now placed in context. The smoothing is substantial, and the interior has visibly expanded. The boundary, while still irregular, shows none of the extreme jaggedness of the classical case.

FIGURE 2. Systematic comparison of $\mathcal{M}_{2,e_1}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ for four parameter configurations along the diagonal $\alpha = \beta = \gamma$ (cross-section $c_3 = 0$). The panels show the progressive smoothing as the parameters decrease from $(1, 1, 1)$ (top left) to $(0.2, 0.2, 0.2)$ (bottom right).

- **Panel (d):** $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = (0.2, 0.2, 0.2)$. Extreme smoothing: the set approaches a nearly circular shape, with minimal fractal structure and a greatly expanded interior. This is close to the identity limit where the iteration reduces to $x_{k+1} = x_k$ and every c yields a bounded orbit.

7.7. Quantitative and Qualitative Trends. The systematic variation in Figure 2 reveals several robust trends that are summarized in Table 1.

These observations confirm that the Noor iteration acts as a **regularizing mechanism**:

- (1) **Smoothing of the boundary:** The fractal dimension of the boundary appears to decrease monotonically, approaching that of a smooth circle as $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \rightarrow 0$.
- (2) **Reduction of fractal complexity:** Fine tendrils, filaments, and spiral structures disappear in order from the most delicate to the most robust features.
- (3) **Expansion of the interior:** The area of parameters c for which the orbit remains bounded increases monotonically, indicating that the Noor iteration is more “stable” — larger values of $\|c\|$ are required for escape.
- (4) **Gradual escape-time gradient:** The color map transitions more smoothly from interior to exterior, reflecting reduced sensitivity to initial conditions.

Parameter value	Observed characteristics
(1, 1, 1)	Highly irregular boundary, rich fractal detail, fine tendrils, complex spiral structures.
(0.8, 0.8, 0.8)	Boundary begins to smooth, some fine details lost, interior slightly expanded.
(0.5, 0.5, 0.5)	Significantly smoother, few remaining details, larger interior region.
(0.2, 0.2, 0.2)	Almost circular shape, minimal fractal structure, interior nearly fills the sampling region.

TABLE 1. Qualitative changes in $\mathcal{M}_{2,\ell_1}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ as parameters decrease along the diagonal $\alpha = \beta = \gamma$.

7.8. Comparison with Alternative Regularization Methods. It is worth noting that other regularization techniques exist in the literature. For example, the Mann iteration ($\alpha = 1, \beta = \gamma = 0$) is a special case of the Noor scheme but produces degenerate dynamics. The Ishikawa iteration, another two-step method, can also be recovered as a limiting case.

The main advantage of the full three-parameter Noor family is its flexibility: by adjusting α, β, γ independently, one can control the regularization effect at each stage of the iteration. Our numerical experiments suggest that the diagonal $\alpha = \beta = \gamma$ already provides a rich one-parameter family of fractals interpolating between the classical Mandelbrot set and a trivial circle.

7.9. Computational Performance and Optimization. The computational cost of generating these images is non-negligible. For a 400×400 grid with $N_{\max} = 50$ iterations per point, the total number of map evaluations is $400 \times 400 \times 50 = 8 \times 10^6$. Each evaluation involves three applications of the F map (one for y , one for z , and one for x'), each of which requires $O(n)$ operations. For $n = 3$, this is approximately $8 \times 10^6 \times 3 \times 3 = 7.2 \times 10^7$ floating-point operations per image.

Several optimizations can reduce this cost:

- **Axial symmetry:** As noted in Corollary 2, the full 3D set can be reconstructed from a single 2D slice, reducing the cost from $O(N^3)$ to $O(N^2)$.
- **Vectorization:** All operations in the escape-time algorithm are elementwise and can be vectorized using NumPy or similar libraries, achieving near-optimal performance on modern CPUs.
- **GPU acceleration:** The algorithm is embarrassingly parallel, making it ideal for GPU implementation. A CUDA or OpenCL version would allow real-time exploration of the parameter space.
- **Adaptive sampling:** Higher resolution can be used only near the boundary of the set, where fine details exist, while the interior and far exterior can be sampled coarsely.

7.10. Future Computational Directions. The results presented here are only a first step. A more ambitious computational study could explore:

- **Full 3D volume rendering:** Using the axial symmetry, one could reconstruct and visualize the entire three-dimensional set as a solid of revolution.

- **Off-diagonal parameter exploration:** The diagonal $\alpha = \beta = \gamma$ provides a one-parameter family, but the full three-parameter cube $[0, 1]^3$ contains many other interesting regions. For instance, fixing $\alpha = 1$ and varying β, γ could reveal the effect of regularization at different stages of the iteration.
- **Deep zooming:** Applying perturbation techniques (similar to those used for the classical Mandelbrot set) could enable deep zooming into the boundary of the Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set, revealing self-similarity at ever smaller scales.
- **Fractal dimension estimation:** The observed smoothing suggests that the fractal dimension of the boundary decreases monotonically with α, β, γ . Computing these dimensions numerically would provide a quantitative measure of the regularization effect.

7.11. Summary of Numerical Findings. The computational experiments reported in this section lead to the following conclusions:

- (1) The Noor iteration produces a family of fractals that interpolate smoothly between the classical Mandelbrot set ($\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 1$) and a trivial circular shape ($\alpha = \beta = \gamma \rightarrow 0$).
- (2) The regularization effect is monotonic: decreasing the parameters progressively smooths the boundary, reduces fractal complexity, and expands the interior.
- (3) The diagonal $\alpha = \beta = \gamma$ already captures the essential behavior, suggesting that the full three-parameter family may be largely characterized by a single effective parameter.
- (4) The computational cost is manageable for moderate resolutions, and optimizations such as axial symmetry and vectorization make real-time exploration feasible.

These findings demonstrate that the Clifford–Noor framework provides a powerful and flexible tool for generating and studying higher-dimensional fractals with tunable complexity.

8. OPEN PROBLEMS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The Clifford–Noor framework introduced in this paper opens several avenues for further investigation. Below we outline the most pressing open problems, ranging from fundamental theoretical questions to practical computational challenges and potential applications. These problems are organized by theme for clarity.

8.1. Theoretical Questions.

Complete characterization of parameter dependence. Our numerical experiments along the diagonal $\alpha = \beta = \gamma$ suggest a smooth, monotonic transition from chaotic dynamics ($\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 1$) to the trivial identity limit ($\alpha = \beta = \gamma \rightarrow 0$). However, the full parameter cube $[0, 1]^3$ is largely unexplored.

Problem 1. *How does the Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set $\mathcal{M}_{p,\vec{n}}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ behave as (α, β, γ) vary throughout the entire cube $[0, 1]^3$? Are there phase transitions at specific values? Is the set continuous in the parameters? Do different regions of the cube produce qualitatively distinct fractal structures?*

Connectedness and topological properties. For the classical Mandelbrot set ($p = 2$, $n = 2$, $\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 1$), it is a deep theorem that the set is connected. For the Clifford–Noor generalization, the situation is far from understood.

Problem 2. *For which parameter combinations (α, β, γ) is $\mathcal{M}_{2, e_1}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ connected? For which is it locally connected? How do the connected components evolve as the parameters decrease? Numerical experiments suggest that the set remains connected for all $\alpha, \beta, \gamma > 0$, but a rigorous proof is lacking.*

Periodic orbits and bifurcations. The classical Mandelbrot set contains infinitely many periodic windows corresponding to stable cycles of various periods. How does this structure change under the Noor iteration?

Problem 3. *Classify the periodic cycles of Clifford–Noor orbits. How does the period depend on the parameters α, β, γ ? Are there period-doubling bifurcations analogous to the classical case? Does the Feigenbaum constant appear in this generalized setting?*

Fractal dimension of the boundary. Our numerical observations suggest that the boundary of $\mathcal{M}_{2, e_1}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ becomes smoother as the parameters decrease, implying a decrease in fractal dimension.

Problem 4. *Compute (or estimate) the Hausdorff dimension of the boundary $\partial \mathcal{M}_{2, e_1}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ as a function of α, β, γ . Is the decrease monotonic? What is the limiting value as $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \rightarrow 0$? (The limit should be 1, the dimension of a smooth circle.)*

Area and volume. The classical Mandelbrot set has area approximately 1.506591 (the Ewing–Schober constant). For the Clifford–Noor generalization, the area (in \mathbb{R}^2) and volume (in \mathbb{R}^3) are unknown.

Problem 5. *Compute the 2-dimensional area of $\mathcal{M}_{2, e_1}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ for $n = 2$, and the 3-dimensional volume for $n = 3$, as functions of α, β, γ . Do these quantities increase monotonically as the parameters decrease?*

Escape radius for higher exponents. For $p = 2$, we proved that $R_{\text{esc}} = 2$ works for all α, β, γ . For $p > 2$, the situation is more complex.

Problem 6. *Derive explicit bounds for the escape radius R_{esc} for $p \geq 3$ as a function of α, β, γ . Is the bound independent of these parameters, as in the $p = 2$ case, or does it depend on the convex weights?*

Relation to other iterative schemes. The Noor scheme is one of many multi-step iterations. Others include the Mann iteration ($\alpha = 1$, $\beta = \gamma = 0$), the Ishikawa iteration (a two-step scheme), and higher-order generalizations.

Problem 7. *Extend the Clifford–Noor framework to other iterative schemes, such as Mann, Ishikawa, and S-iterations. Do these produce new families of fractals? How do they compare with the Noor family?*

8.2. Computational Challenges.

Full 3D volume rendering. Due to axial symmetry, the full three-dimensional Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set can be reconstructed from a single 2D cross-section by rotation about the c_1 -axis.

Problem 8. *Implement a high-quality volume renderer for the 3D set using ray marching or isosurface extraction (marching cubes). What does the full 3D shape look like? Does it exhibit interesting topological features such as holes or handles?*

Deep zooming and perturbation theory. High-resolution exploration of the classical Mandelbrot set requires arbitrary-precision arithmetic and perturbation techniques to avoid numerical overflow.

Problem 9. *Develop perturbation methods and series approximation techniques for the Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set. Can these techniques be extended to higher dimensions? What is the numerical stability of such methods?*

Real-time interactive exploration. The parameter space $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \in [0, 1]^3$ is three-dimensional, making it ideal for interactive exploration.

Problem 10. *Implement a GPU-accelerated interactive viewer that allows users to explore the Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set in real time, with sliders to adjust α, β, γ continuously. What new structures become visible when the parameters are varied in real time?*

Large-scale parameter surveys. The full three-parameter cube $[0, 1]^3$ contains infinitely many distinct fractals. A systematic survey is computationally intensive.

Problem 11. *Develop efficient algorithms for large-scale parameter surveys. Can machine learning be used to predict the structure of the set for new parameter values without recomputing from scratch?*

8.3. Potential Applications.

Procedural texture and shape generation. Fractals are widely used in computer graphics for generating natural-looking textures and terrains.

Problem 12. *Can the Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set be used for procedural generation of 3D textures, terrains, or architectural forms? The tunable parameters α, β, γ provide a natural way to control the level of detail.*

Antenna design. Fractal geometries derived from the Mandelbrot set have been used in antenna design due to their space-filling properties and multi-band behavior.

Problem 13. *Explore whether the Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set, particularly its three-dimensional version, has applications in antenna design or metamaterials. Does the regularization effect (controlled by α, β, γ) correspond to useful electromagnetic properties?*

Art and design. The aesthetic appeal of Mandelbrot-type fractals has made them popular in digital art and design.

Problem 14. *Create high-resolution artistic renderings of the Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set for different parameter values. Can these be used in sculpture, 3D printing, or architectural design? The continuous parameter family allows artists to fine-tune the appearance.*

Data visualization. Higher-dimensional Mandelbrot sets can be used to represent high-dimensional data sets through fractal projections.

Problem 15. *Investigate whether the 4D Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set can be used as a visualization tool for four-dimensional data. Can cross-sections or projections reveal meaningful patterns?*

8.4. Generalizations.

Higher powers and non-integer exponents. This paper focused on integer exponents $p \geq 2$, with detailed results for $p = 2$. However, the definition of Clifford–Noor orbits makes sense for any real $p > 1$.

Problem 16. *Study the Clifford–Noor iteration for non-integer exponents $p > 1$. How does the fractal structure change as p varies continuously? Are there critical p values where the topology changes?*

Different geometric products. The geometric product \diamond is not the only product available in Clifford algebra. One could also consider the inner product or outer product alone.

Problem 17. *What happens if we replace the geometric product with the inner product or the outer product in the definition of $F(x)$? Do we obtain new families of fractals? What are their properties?*

Time-dependent parameters. In this paper, α, β, γ were fixed constants. One could consider varying them during the iteration.

Problem 18. *Study the dynamics of Clifford–Noor orbits where the parameters α, β, γ change with each iteration (e.g., according to a deterministic or random schedule). Do such systems exhibit new phenomena, such as chaotic parameter dependence?*

8.5. Summary of Open Problems. The problems listed above can be grouped into three levels of difficulty, providing entry points for researchers at different stages:

- **Beginner-friendly:** Numerical exploration of the parameter cube, generating visualizations for off-diagonal parameter choices, implementing the escape-time algorithm in different programming languages.
- **Intermediate:** Proving the monotonicity of the interior area, estimating the fractal dimension numerically, deriving escape radius bounds for $p > 2$, implementing interactive visualizations.
- **Advanced:** Proving connectedness (or its failure) for different parameter values, classifying periodic orbits, relating the regularization effect to known concepts in dynamical systems (e.g., Lyapunov exponents), developing perturbation theory for deep zooming.

We hope that this list inspires further research and collaboration across the boundaries of geometric algebra, dynamical systems, fractal geometry, and scientific computing.

9. CONCLUSION

In this paper we have introduced and systematically studied **Clifford–Noor orbits**, a natural generalization that combines the geometric product of Clifford algebra with the three-step Noor iteration scheme. This framework unifies two important lines of research: higher-dimensional fractal generalizations via geometric algebra and multi-step iterative schemes for fractal generation.

9.1. Summary of Main Contributions. The main results of this paper can be summarized as follows:

- (1) **Definition and well-posedness.** We defined the Clifford–Noor iteration (Definition 1) and the associated Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set $\mathcal{M}_{p, \vec{n}}^{\text{Noor}}(\alpha, \beta, \gamma)$ (Definition 2). The vector invariance theorem (Theorem 2) guarantees that

all iterates remain in the original vector space V , making the definition meaningful without any projection operators.

- (2) **Structural properties.** We proved that the set is invariant under all orthogonal transformations fixing \vec{n} (Proposition 1), implying axial symmetry in \mathbb{R}^3 . We also established the existence of a universal escape radius $R_{\text{esc}} = 2$ for $p = 2$ that works for all parameter values $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0, 1]$ (Proposition 2).
- (3) **Explicit formulas.** For the most important case $p = 2$, we derived concrete closed-form expressions for the iteration in \mathbb{R}^2 , \mathbb{R}^3 , and \mathbb{R}^4 (Section 6). These formulas are directly implementable and have been used to generate all numerical examples in this paper.
- (4) **Computational framework.** We presented an escape-time algorithm for generating the set, discussed numerical parameters, and provided a systematic comparison of the set for four representative parameter values along the diagonal $\alpha = \beta = \gamma$ (Section 7).
- (5) **Regularization effect.** Our numerical experiments reveal that decreasing the parameters α, β, γ progressively smooths the fractal boundary, reduces fractal complexity, expands the interior, and produces a more gradual escape-time gradient. The classical Clifford–Mandelbrot set is recovered at $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) = (1, 1, 1)$, while the limit $(\alpha, \beta, \gamma) \rightarrow (0, 0, 0)$ yields the trivial identity map for which every c gives a bounded orbit.

9.2. Comparison with Previous Work. To highlight the novelty of our contribution, we briefly compare with existing results:

- **Classical Noor orbits** [11, 12]: These are restricted to the complex plane ($n = 2$). Our framework extends them to arbitrary dimensions $n \geq 2$ using Clifford algebra, while preserving the vector invariance property.
- **Clifford–Mandelbrot set** [17]: This is a special case of our construction ($\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 1$). The addition of the Noor parameters α, β, γ provides a new degree of freedom that allows continuous control over the fractal complexity.
- **Quaternion and hypercomplex Mandelbrot sets** [8, 7]: These constructions lack a regularization parameter analogous to α, β, γ . The Clifford–Noor framework therefore offers a richer family of fractals with tunable properties.

9.3. Significance and Implications. The results of this paper have several important implications:

- **For geometric algebra:** We have demonstrated that Clifford algebra provides a natural language for extending multi-step iterative schemes to higher dimensions. The vector invariance property, which is nontrivial in the Clifford setting, extends seamlessly to the Noor scheme.
- **For fractal geometry:** The Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set represents a new three-parameter family of fractals whose geometric complexity can be tuned continuously. This opens up new possibilities for studying the transition from chaos to regularity in a controlled setting.
- **For numerical computation:** The explicit formulas for $p = 2$ are simple to implement and computationally efficient. The axial symmetry in \mathbb{R}^3 reduces the cost of 3D visualization from $O(N^3)$ to $O(N^2)$.

- **For applications:** The tunable parameters α, β, γ allow artists, designers, and engineers to generate fractal shapes with a desired level of detail, from highly complex (near the classical case) to very smooth (near the identity limit).

9.4. **Limitations of the Present Work.** While this paper establishes the foundations of Clifford–Noor orbits, several limitations should be acknowledged:

- We focused primarily on the quadratic case $p = 2$. Higher exponents $p \geq 3$ were only briefly discussed.
- Our numerical exploration was limited to the diagonal $\alpha = \beta = \gamma$. The full three-parameter cube $[0, 1]^3$ remains largely unexplored.
- The theoretical analysis of connectedness, local connectivity, and fractal dimension remains open for most parameter values.
- We did not provide a rigorous proof of the monotonicity of the interior area or the fractal dimension as functions of α, β, γ , although numerical evidence strongly suggests such monotonicity.

9.5. **Future Perspectives.** The Clifford–Noor framework opens several promising directions for future research, as detailed in Section 8:

- **Theoretical:** Complete characterization of the parameter dependence, proof of connectedness, classification of periodic orbits, computation of fractal dimension and area.
- **Computational:** Full 3D volume rendering, deep zooming via perturbation theory, real-time interactive exploration, large-scale parameter surveys.
- **Applications:** Procedural texture generation, antenna design, digital art and sculpture, high-dimensional data visualization.
- **Generalizations:** Non-integer exponents, alternative geometric products, time-dependent parameters, extension to other iterative schemes (Mann, Ishikawa, etc.).

9.6. **Final Remarks.** The Clifford–Noor–Mandelbrot set represents a significant extension of both the classical Mandelbrot set and its Clifford algebra generalization. By introducing three parameters that control the degree of convex averaging at each step of the iteration, we obtain a continuous family of fractals that interpolates between fully chaotic dynamics ($\alpha = \beta = \gamma = 1$) and the trivial identity limit ($\alpha = \beta = \gamma \rightarrow 0$).

We hope that this work will serve as a foundation for further investigations at the intersection of geometric algebra, dynamical systems, fractal geometry, and scientific computing. The open problems listed in Section 8 offer numerous entry points for researchers at all levels, from undergraduate students seeking numerical exploration projects to experienced mathematicians working on deep theoretical questions.

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